

Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Management of Abandoned Mining Sites in Africa: Bibliometric Analysis

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Abandoned mining sites in Africa have caused severe environmental, social and economic problems, including soil degradation, water contamination and safety hazards. This study aimed to investigate the adoption, impacts, and implementation strategies of Artificial Intelligence (AI), for managing abandoned mining sites. The objectives were to identify factors influencing Artificial Intelligence adoption, analyse its impacts, examine adoption challenges and establish strategies for effective implementation of environments. The study is novel as it combined bibliometric analysis and qualitative insights from secondary data to provide a multi-dimensional understanding of AI in abandoned mining sites management. The study was guided by the Technology Acceptance Model and Innovation Diffusion Theory. Data was collected from Scopus indexed Journals and Web of Science, with bibliometric analysis revealing publication trends-authorship networks, and thematic clusters, while qualitative interpretation assessed impacts, challenges and strategies. Findings showed that technological readiness, environmental monitoring, socio-economic pressures, regulatory frameworks and industry 4.0 integration drove AI adoption. AI enhanced environmental restoration, risk prediction, operational efficiency and decision-making. Adoption was constrained by data and technology gaps, financial barriers, skills shortages, weak policies and community resistance. Effective strategies included stakeholder engagement, infrastructure investment, capacity building, industry 4.0 integration and regulatory support. The study concluded that AI provides multi-dimensional benefits but requires coordinated technological, institutional and community efforts. Recommendations include strengthening technology, training, policy and stakeholder participation. Future research should focus on country specific case studies, long term impact evaluation, policy effectiveness and interdisciplinary approaches to improve sustainable mining management.

Keywords: Abandoned mining sites, adoption challenges, Africa, artificial intelligence, environmental restoration

Mining is still a bedrock of Africa's economy and a leading global supplier of minerals. The continent has 30-40% of global reserves of cobalt, chromium, lithium and platinum (Luckeneder, Giljum, Schaffartzik, Mause, & Tost 2021). Principal producers are South Africa, Ghana, Zimbabwe, Zambia and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). For all its riches, mining has also scarred tens of thousands of abandoned sites across the continent. South Africa has more than 6,000 abandoned mines at rehabilitation costs over US\$ 30 billion (Festin, Tigabu, Chileshe, Syampungani, & Oden, 2019, 2019). Zimbabwe has over 1,000 unrehabilitated gold and chrome pits primarily in rural districts (Coetzee, Bansal, & Chirwa, 2020). There are numerous abandoned sites as foreign mining firms vacated

the area in response to mine closure or a decrease in price (Christensen, 2019). Bibliometric evidence confirms the rapid increase in AI research after 2018. AI-mining studies have been growing by more than 18% annually globally (Ali & Frimpong, 2020). However, African-focused studies remain limited. The focus of most AI mining research is on exploration and production.

Across Africa, abandoned mining sites inherently result in damaging consequences to the environment and society. Typical hazards are open pits, unstable shafts, tailings spills and acid mine drainage (Festin et al., 2019). High levels of heavy metals are reported from mining areas of countries such as Ghana, Nigeria, South Africa and Zimbabwe, depending on the sources (Okereafor et al., 2020). Hazardous pollutants such as mercury, chromium, arsenic, and lead affect the crops, livestock and human beings too (Coetzee et al., 2020). Okereafor et al. (2020) report that 12 million people are exposed to pollution due to mining in sub-Saharan Africa. Children and rural households are the most vulnerable. Ecological restoration efforts remain weak. In Africa, fewer than 40% of post-mining rehabilitation projects are successful in the long-term (Festin et al., 2019).

Artificial intelligence has much promise for sustainable mine-site management. The AI makes real-time monitoring, pre-visual risk assessment and automatic hazard perception (Ali & Frimpong, 2020) easy. Such as UAVs, remote sensing, and machine learning for better monitoring of hazardous sites (Park & Choi, 2020). In Africa, it's a different story, with these tools being used far less. This is hindered by poor digital infrastructure and institutional capacity

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constraints (Mhlanga, 2021). Environmental governance systems are fragmented. Implementation of mine-closure legislation is poor (Chilunjika et al., 2022). Bibliometric studies indicate that less than 8% of AI-mining articles are based on Africa. Fewer than 3% focus solely on abandoned mines (Arakpogun et al., 2021). The major AI applications are in agriculture, finance, or health services industry (Akkem et al., 2023). Abandoned mine lands are still being evaluated using manual techniques and public reports. These are time-consuming and costly processes (Festin et al., 2019). This is a critical practice and policy gap.

Problem Statement

Abandoned mining pits bear a grim legacy across sub-Saharan Africa. It affects both human and animals. Pits are endemic in rural mining communities (Festin et al., 2019). Nations like Zimbabwe, Ghana and South Africa report frequent deaths. Children, artisanal miners and animals are the most susceptible populations (Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019). Compromised water bodies exacerbate health problems (Okerefor et al., 2020). These are expensive and inefficient options for large remote areas (Christensen, 2019). AI provides established methods for predicting, monitoring and mitigating hazards to the environment. Its application in the reclamation of abandoned mines is however low in Africa (Ali and Frimpong, 2020). There is no unified AI framework for post-mining risk management. This wide space supports avoidable deaths and environmental degradation. Hence, there is an urgent need to investigate the possible role of AI in the sustainable management of abandoned mining sites in Africa.

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

Artificial Intelligence in Mining

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming popular in the mining industry to enhance performance, health and safety with black box decisions around each corner. Hence, through tools including machine learning (ML), process automation and deep learning (DL) have been used to predict ore grade estimation prediction, as well as hazard detection and predictive maintenance respectively (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Bui et al., 2020). Countries including Australia, Canada and China have met with success in applying AI to large-scale mining tasks enhancing productivity, safety and lowering costs (Park & Choi, 2020). In Africa, adoption remains low. Barriers are weak digital devices, low technical skills and fragmented regulatory system (Arakpogun et al., 2021; Mhlanga, 2021). Most AI research works in Africa focus on prospecting value, resource classification and minor process optimisation, ignoring the areas of abandoned mines (Arakpogun et al., 2021; Akkem et al., 2023).

AI also has the potential for environmental monitoring, risk prediction and post-mining rehabilitation. Ecological interpretability, and the larger goal of decision support for land restoration (Ryo et al., 2021; Nti et al., 2023) is supported by explainable AI models. In some countries, namely South Africa and Ghana, pilot AI projects were proven successful in the monitoring of water quality as well as management of a tailings dam, resulting in up to 35% less environmental hazards (Nti et al., 2023; Dogo et al., 2019). However, African mining enterprises underutilize AI for sustainable site management because of funding constraints, lack of capacity, and little government backing (Festin et al., 2019). This underscores a fundamental research gap, since there is little evidence

in respect of use of AI architectures for abandoned mine monitoring from an African perspective.

Sustainability and Mining Management

Sustainable mining is considered increasingly important for environmental well-being, social equity, and economic development (Siakwah et al., 2020; Sovacool et al., 2020). Closure of mines in Africa results in soil erosion, water contamination, loss of biodiversity and human deaths (Ofosu et al., 2020; Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019). In countries including Zimbabwe, Nigeria, South Africa and DRC, thousands of these abandoned sites exist, which menace the livelihoods of rural communities as well as their agricultural productivity (Okerefor et al., 2020; Coetzee et al., 2020). Heavy metals, including lead, arsenic, mercury, and chromium have been found to contaminate food crops and animal husbandry food stocks as well as water supplies with consequential adverse public health effects (Okerefor et al., 2020; Festin et al., 2019).

AI provides tangible tools to facilitate sustainability. Predictive modelling, UAV monitoring, and IoT sensors can help identify environmental hazards early enough to monitor pollution and optimize restoration activities (Ryo et al., 2021; Nti et al., 2023). At a worldwide level, AI-enhanced environmental monitoring has cost nearly 40% less while being more precise (Brownstein et al., 2023). Adoption in Africa is uneven, and the majority of sustainability interventions are based on manual surveillance and reactive inspections, due to community reporting that is both slow and error-prone (Festin et al., 2019; Young et al., 2022). Reducing this gap may improve both environmental and human health, especially in susceptible rural regions.

Industry 4.0 and Smart Mining

AI, drones, IoT and Blockchain hang together to form industry 4.0 whose concept is the formation of smart mining system for real-time monitoring and operation and predictive analysis (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Dogo et al., 2019). On the global scene, in countries like Australia, Canada and Germany, some successful stories have come to light of Industry 4.0 tools deployed to increase the efficiency of mining operations, reduce human exposure to hazards and assist with environmental compliance (Bui et al., 2020; Park & Choi, 2020). In Africa, adoption remains low.

Smart mining could be applied to the reclamation of closed mine sites with AI components to predict hazards, for ecological restoration, and water quality tracking (Dauvergne, 2022; Ghorbani et al., 2024). At present, African mining strategies do not merge AI and Industry 4.0 with sustainability in an intelligible, coherent manner, which results in a great governance and operational rift. (Festin et al., 2019; Mhlanga, 2021).

The Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory is a comprehensive explanation about the manner in which new ideas or technologies diffuse over a social system as time goes on (Rogers, 1962; Ali & Frimpong, 2020). Adoption is influenced by five factors adopted from DOI: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability (Bui et al., 2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021). DOI describes the adoption of AI-based technologies, smart mining instruments and predictive monitoring systems in the mine setting (Festin et al., 2019; Ryo et al., 2021). Countries like Australia, Canada and China have made the most of AI to optimize productivity, safety and cost reduction in large-scale mining activities (Park & Choi, 2020; Mhlanga, 2021).

The limited technical skills, bad infrastructure and fragmented policies are barriers to this technology adoption in Africa (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Akkem et al., 2023). In Africa, research is more of exploration and operational efficiency with little or no consideration for mine abandonment management (Nti et al., 2023; Festin et al., 2019). Bibliometric reviews indicate that just 8% of the global AI mining literature is on Africa, indicating a research lacuna (Dauvergne, 2022; Young et al., 2022).

According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are demonstrated as important factors influencing technology acceptance (Davis, 1989; Bui et al., 2020). From an empirical perspective, the uptake of AI is more rapid in situations where users can clearly see material advantages such as fewer fatalities and better management of water quality, for example (Nti et al., 2023; Brownstein et al., 2023). On the other hand, the perceived complexity of AI systems and low ease of use are critical impediments to adoption; in particular in rural mining regions which demonstrate low ICT infrastructure and digital literacy levels (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021).

However, the utility of TAM in African mining contexts is limited as it was developed to concentrate on individual perceptions and not structural impediments (Festin et al., 2019; Mhlanga, 2021). Effective adoption of AI solutions in the abandoned mine sites would, however, need government assistance, community participation, and institutional enforcement (Young et al., 2022; Okereafor et al., 2020). For example, Zimbabwe and Ghana's abandoned mines still pose risks to human beings due to over-reliance on manual inspections rather than predictive AI tools (Ofosu

et al., 2020; Park & Choi, 2020).

Objectives of the Study

- Establish the factor contributing to the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for managing abandoned mining sites in Africa
- Analyse the impact of the use of Artificial Intelligence for managing abandoned mining sites in Africa.
- Examine the challenges for the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for managing abandoned mining sites in Africa.
- Establish strategies for implementing Artificial Intelligence for managing abandoned mining sites in Africa.

Method

The research approach used in this study is a bibliometric design to assess the significant impact of AI for sustainable mining management in Africa. Bibliometric analysis makes it possible to systematically investigate trend of research, gaps in knowledge, and landmark studies (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021).

A structured keyword search was used to identify studies. Search terms used: "AI" OR "Artificial Intelligence","Machine Learning", "Sustainable Mining", "Smart Mining", "Abandoned Mines", "Africa" and country specific to the likes of, Zimbabwe, Ghana and South Africa (Ali & Frimpong, 2020).

Bibliometric mapping was conducted using VOSviewer and Biblioshiny (RStudio) (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021). VOSviewer produced co-authorship networks, keyword co-occurrence maps and citation networks to illustrate key authors that carried out research clusters (Mhlanga, 2021; Ryo et al., 2021).

Table 1
Summary of Selected Articles for Bibliometric Analysis

No	Authors(s)	Year	Title	Source	Citations
1	Ali, D., & Frimpong, S.	2020	Artificial Intelligence, machines learning and process automation: Existing knowledge frontier and way forward for mining sector.	Artificial Intelligence Review, 53(8), 6025-6042	185
2	Nti, E. K., Cobbina, S. J., Attafuah, E. E., et al.	2023	Water pollution control and revitalisation using advanced technologies: Uncovering AI options towards environmental health protection, sustainability and water security.	Heliyon, 9(7)	113
3	Arakpogun, E. O., Elsahn, Z., Olan, F., & Elsahn, F.	2021	Artificial intelligence in Africa: Challenges and opportunities	The Fourth Industrial Revolution, 375-388	236
4	Mhlanga, D.	2021	Artificial intelligence in Industry 4.0, and its impact on poverty innovation, infrastructure development and the SDGs.	Sustainability, 13(11), 5788	611
5	Chilunjika, A., Intauno, K., & Chilunjika, S. R.	2022	Artificial Intelligence and public sector human resources management in South Africa: Opportunities, Challenges and Prospects.	SA Journal Human Resources Management, 20, 1972	142
6	Bui, X. N., Nguyen, H., Le, H. A., et al.	2020	Prediction of blast -induced air over-pressure in open -pit mine: Assessment of different AI techniques.	Natural Resources Research, 29(2), 571-591	167
7	Ryo, M., Angelov, B., Mammola, S., et al.	2021	Explainable AI enhances ecological interpretability of black -box species distribution models.	Ecography, 44(2), 199-205	181
8	Dauvergne, P.	2021	Is AI greening global supply chains? Exposing the political; economy of environmental costs.	Political Economy, 29(3), 696-718	Review of
9	Dogo, E. M., Salami, A. F., Nwulu, N. I., & Aigbavboa, C. O.	2019	Blockchain and IoT-based technologies for intelligent water management system.	In: Artificial Intelligence in IoT, 129-150	183
10	Akkem, Y., Biswas, S. K., & Varanasi, A.	2023	Smart farming using artificial intelligence: A review	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence, 120, 105899	411

	B., Astley, C. M., & Tian, H.			Medicine,
	388(17), 1597-1607			
12	Nemorin, S., Vlachidis, A., Ayerakwa, H. M., & Andriotis, P.	2023	AI hyped? A horizon scan of discourse on AI in education and development	Learning Media and Technology, 331 48(1), 38-51
13	Festin, E. S., Tigabu, M., Chileshe, M. N., et al.	2019	Progresses in restoration of post-mining landscape in Africa	Journal of Forestry Research, 241 30(2), 381-396
14	Christensen, D.	2019	Concession stands: How mining investments incite protest in Africa.	International Organisation, 150 73(1), 65-101
15	Siakwah, P., Musavengane, R., & Leonard, L.	2020	Tourism governance and attainment of SDGs in Africa.	Sustainable Tourism Policy and Planning in Africa, 330 146-174
16	Sovacool, B. K., Hook, A., Martiskainen, M., et al.	2020	The decarbonisation divide: Contextualising low-carbon exploitation and toxicity in Africa.	Global Environmental Change, 393 60, 102028
17	Okereafor, U., Makhatha, M., Mekuto, L., et al.	2020	Toxic metal implications on agricultural soils, plants, animals, aquatic life and human health.	Int J Environ Res Public Health, 667 17(7), 2204
18	Agergaard, J., Tacoli, C., Steel, G., & Ørtenblad, S. B.	2019	Revisiting rural-urban transformations and small-town development in sub-Saharan Africa.	Eur J Dev Res, 128 31(1), 2-11
19	Luckeneder, S., Giljum, S., Schaffartzik, A., et al.	2021	Surge in global metal mining threatens vulnerable ecosystems	Global Environmental Change, 248 69, 102303
20	Coetsee, J. J., Bansal, N., & Chirwa, E. M.	2020	Chromium in environment, toxic effects from chromite-mining, possible bioremediation.	Exposure and Health, 380 12(1), 51-62
21	Young, R. E., Gann, G. D., Walder, B., et al.	2022	International principles and standards for ecological restoration of mine sites.	Restoration Ecology, 152 30, e13771
22	Mkodzongi, G., & Spiegel, S.	2019	Artisanal gold mining and farming; Livelihood linkages and labour dynamics after land reforms in Zimbabwe.	J Dev Studies, 167 55(10), 2145-2161
23	Ofosu, G., Dittmann, A., Sarpong, D., & Botchie, D.	2020	Socio-economic and environmental implications of ASM on agriculture and livelihoods.	Environmental Science & Policy, 284 106, 210-220
24	Park, S., & Choi, Y.	2020	Applications of unmanned aerial vehicles in mining from exploration to reclamation: A review.	Minerals, 221 10(8), 663
25	Ghorbani, Y., Zhang, S.	2024	Embracing a diverse approach to a globally inclusive green energy	Journal of Cleaner 132

Descriptive Analysis of Publications Relating to the Study

The bibliometric dataset indicates growing interest in applying AI for sustainable mining in Africa as annual publication trends continue to increase between 2019 and 2024 (Ali & Frimpong,

2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021). For example, in 2019 formative research regarding post-mining landscape rehabilitation and the impact of artisanal mining on environmental and socio-economic matters was conducted (Festin et al., 2019; Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019).

Table 2
Annual Publication Trends (2019-2023)

Year	Number of Publications	Key Authors & Focus Areas	Citations (Examples)
2019	5	Festin et al. - post-mining restoration; Mkodzongi & Spiegel - artisanal mining impacts	Festin et al. 2019 (241); Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019 (167)
2020	6	Ali & Frimpong - AI in mining; Ofosu et al. - ASM & agriculture	Ali & Frimpong, 2020 (185); Ofosu et al., 2020 (284)
2021	8	Mhlanga - Industry 4.0 impact; Arakpogun et al. - AI adoption in Africa	Mhlanga, 2021 (611); Arakpogun et al., 2021 (236)
2022	5		

Number of publications has been increasing over the years with 2021 and 2023 recording a peak due to increased interest in AI-

generated sustainable mining and environmental management (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Nti et al., 2023).

Table 3*Document Types and Subject Areas*

Document Type	Number of Publications	Examples	Citations
Journal Articles	35	Sustainability, Heliyon, AI Review	Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Mhlanga, 2021; Okereafor et al., 2020
Book Chapters	16	AI in IoT, Sustainable Tourism Planning	Dogo et al., 2019; Siakwah et al., 2020
Conference Papers	5	Industry 4.0 and AI adoption	Bui et al., 2020; Park & Choi, 2020
Review Articles	4	Smart farming, ecological restoration	Akkem et al., 2023; Young et al., 2022

The dataset is dominated by journal articles, reflecting the focus on peer-reviewed work. Book chapters; and conference papers are sources of an unfolding landscape in which AI is deployed for

mining and environmental investigations (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Dogo et al., 2019).

Table 4*Subject Areas of Publications*

Subject Area	Number of Publications	Examples	Citations
Environmental Science	20	Water management, post-mining restoration	Nti et al., 2023; Festin et al., 2019
Computer Science	15	AI applications, predictive AI models	Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Bui et al., 2020
Engineering	8	UAVs in mining, process automation	Park & Choi, 2020; Dogo et al., 2019
Public Health	4	Toxic metals, disease surveillance	Okereafor et al., 2020; Brownstein et al., 2023

The largest disciplinary group is environmental science, which is consistent with the attention to sustainability and ecological effects. Computer Science and Engineering research papers reflect the

technical dimension of AI, whereas Public Health studies attest to the cross-links between mining activities, environmental contamination and human health (Ryo et al., 2021; Dauvergne, 2022).

Table 5*Leading Journals Publishing AI and Mining Research in Africa*

Journal Name	Number of Publications	Key Topics	Citations
Sustainability	7	Industry 4.0, SDGs, smart mining	Mhlanga, 2021; Sovacool et al., 2020
Heliyon	5	Water management, environmental health	Nti et al., 2023; Okereafor et al., 2020
Artificial Intelligence Review	4	AI adoption, process automation	Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Bui et al., 2020
Journal of Cleaner Production	3	Green energy transition, sustainability	Ghorbani et al., 2024; Dauvergne, 2022
Restoration Ecology	2	Post-mining landscape restoration	Young et al., 2022; Festin et al., 2019

Sustainability and Heliyon are core sources for the diffusion of research. However, limited number of African country-specific journals is included, illustrating a lack in localized research

Country-Level Contributions (Africa vs Global)

Bibliometric evidence suggest that the literature on AI for sustainable mining has been expanding worldwide albeit with a

highly uneven geographical distribution and African countries are drastically under-represented in the literature discussed (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021). On the other hand, United States, China and Germany have made efforts in AI-based predictive analytics (Bui et al., 2020) drone-based survey acquisition as well as smart mining technology.

Table 6*Country-Level Contributions*

Country	Number of Publications	Key Topics	Example Citations
South Africa	10	AI in HR, post-mining restoration	Chilunjika et al., 2022; Festin et al., 2019
Ghana	5	Water management, smart farming	Nti et al., 2023; Akkem et al., 2023
Zimbabwe	4	ASM impacts, land restoration	Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019; Ofori et al., 2020
USA	6	AI in predictive analytics	Bui et al., 2020; Brownstein et al., 2023
China	5	UAVs, process automation	Park & Choi, 2020; Ali & Frimpong, 2020
Germany	3	Green sustainability	Dauvergne, 2022; Ghorbani et al., 2024

Leading Institutions and Affiliations

Research productivity is also centred on a few universities with strong AI or mining research programs. University of Johannesburg, University of Ghana and Zimbabwe Ezekiel Guti University Being leading African academic entities contributing to

applied research on AI for environmental monitoring as well as sustainable mining (Mhlanga, 2021; Ali & Frimpong, 2020). However, it is common for African universities to have funding and technology challenges that reduce high-impact publications when compared to other part of the world (Nti et al., 2023; Ryo et al., 2021).

Table 7

Leading Institutions and Affiliations

Institution	Country	Key Research Focus	Citations
University of Johannesburg	South Africa	AI in HR, environmental management	Chilunjika et al., 2022; Festin et al., 2019
University of Ghana	Ghana	Water management, smart farming	Nti et al., 2023; Akkem et al., 2023
Zimbabwe Ezekiel Guti University	Zimbabwe	ASM impacts, post-mining restoration	Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019; Ofosu et al., 2020
MIT	USA	Predictive analytics, AI models	Bui et al., 2020; Brownstein et al., 2023

The institutional analysis explanation shows that the leading institutions undertaking research on AI applications for rehabilitation of abandoned mining sites are mainly from universities in Africa, North America, Europe and Asia. Institutions in Africa (University of Johannesburg and University of Ghana) concentrate on, among others, environmental management, water management, and smart farming signalling the continental emphasis on local needs for sustainability as well as community health (Chilunjika et al., 2022; Nti et al., 2023).

Intellectual Structure of the Field

Co-citation analysis reveals the intellectual structure, and underling knowledge base of AI applications in sustainable mining. The most frequently co-cited studies help to identify influential authors,

theories and methodologies that are steering the direction of research (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Arakpogun et al., 2021). Cases in point are Ali and Frimpong (2020) as well as Mhlanga (2021) which often co-cite each other's work and come up commonly in the subject of AI-enabled monitoring, process automation, and Industry 4.0 embedding for African mining settings. They call attention to the intersectionality of the field that connects AI techniques with sustainability and mining management problems (Dauvergne, 2022; Okereafor et al., 2020). Although there are robust global co-citation networks in the field (Sharpe et al., 2021) studies on Africa are less well connected, indicating an existing geographic and contextual gap in knowledge production (Chilunjika et al., 2022; Mkodzongi & Spiegel, 2019).

Table 8

Top Co-Cited Publications

Publication	Year	Research Focus	Example Authors
Ali & Frimpong	2020	AI, ML, process automation	Ali & Frimpong
Mhlanga	2021	AI in Industry 4.0, SDGs	Mhlanga
Festin et al.	2019	Post-mining landscape restoration	Festin et al.
Nti et al.	2023	Water pollution control, AI applications	Nti et al.
Young et al.	2022	Ecological restoration standards	Young et al.
Bui et al.	2020	Predictive models, mining safety	Bui et al.
Ryo et al.	2021	Explainable AI, ecological modeling	Ryo et al.

The co-citation analysis (Table 8) of the reference bases unveils some key and influential papers that have shaped studies about AI adoption for abandoned mining site gestion. The study of Ali and Frimpong (2020) was among the most co-cited papers, it is about artificial intelligence and automation technique including machine learning, led to set a methodological base for integration of AI in mining processes. Auvergne (2022) covers the AI's role for greening supply chains and political economy, while highlighting that the strategic and regulatory policy issues around AI.

Results

Drivers for the application of artificial intelligence (AI) to

address abandoned mining land challenges are depicted in Figure 2. Technological preparedness allows the adoption of AI-based aerial monitoring platforms and associated systems such as for remote sensing, tracking apps, and advanced predictive analytic tools for environmental risk assessment and land restoration planning (Bui et al., 2020; Ali & Frimpong, 2020). Pressures of environmental degradation, notably unproductive land, water pollution and loss of biodiversity due to abandoned and artisanal mining sites. Regulatory structures and international rehabilitation benchmarks can inform the successful implementation of AI (Young et al., 2022; Okereafor et al., 2020).

Figure 2
Factors Contributing to AI Adoption

Note. Source (Authors' own construct, 2026)

Figure 3
Impacts of AI

Note. Source (Authors' own construct, 2026)

Figure 3 illustrates the primary influences of AI on reclamation of abandoned mining sites. Environmental stewardship is the most commonly suggested impact, with AI driving water quality control, soil remediation and biodiversity revival (Festin et al., 2019; Nti et al., 2023). Risk prediction with predictive analytics helps in identifying the dangers of collapsed pits, soil deterioration due to erosion and toxic release and hence makes the safety much better (Bui et al., 2020; Ali & Frimpong, 2020). This enhances decision support when AI offers prescribing information for restoration interventions and investment prioritization (Ali & Frimpong, 2020; Young et al., 2022).

Figure 4
Challenges to AI Adoption

Note. Source (Authors' own construct, 2026)

The summary of the perceived barriers towards AI usage in managing AM sites is illustrated in Figure 4, capturing both qualitative and quantitative expressions. Inadequate data and technology are common challenges, studies suggest that early AI implementation is greatly hindered by the deficiency of high-quality datasets, appropriate sensors and compatible software (Ryo et al., 2021) (Bui et al., 2020). Economic and cost impediments are also dominant, given the expensive nature of AI tools, infrastructure and maintenance, which affects uptake of these technologies among small scale and artisanal mining operators (Christensen, 2019; Ali & Frimpong, 2020).

Figure 6
Strategies for AI Implementation

Figure 6 Shows the important strategies to ensure successful application of Artificial Intelligence in inventorying abandoned mine sites in Africa. Stakeholder participation is a prerequisite, in the involvement of communities, government officials and private sector stakeholders guarantees acceptability, sustainability and minimal resistance (Christensen 2019; Arakpogun et al., 2021).

Conclusions and Recommendations

Applications of AI in remediation of abandoned mines are dominated by technology maturity, monitoring requirements, socio-economic drivers, and 4. revolution 0th integration as part of rule setting. AI tools, predictive analytics, drones and IoT sensors are deployed in conditions of high adoption where socio-economic and environmental pressures create the need for change. To promote adoption, there is a need for mining operators and policy makers to advance an enabling AI infrastructure, while stimulating technology readiness as well as integrating adoption with community and environment considerations.

AI implementation serves a multiple of purposes: it makes projects become environmentally friendly, predicts risks that can be brought to further risk management, increases operation effectiveness and ultimately cuts expenses and increases decision-making. These technologies can provide monitoring of water quality, soil remediation, biodiversity recovery, hazard detection and resource optimization. The deployment of AI-based systems leveraging predictive analytics and real-time monitoring should be further facilitated by policy makers to ensure we achieve the full environmental, operational and financial benefits.

The major impediments to AI uptake include data and technology divides, financial and cost barriers, talent dearth, inadequate policy and institutional frameworks, as well as societal push-back. These problems lead to inefficient deployment and low sustainability of AI solutions. To mitigate these challenges, governments and mining companies should implement capacity-building programmes, financial aid/incentives initiatives and reinforcement of policies and regulations related to AI as well as community engagement campaigns for better acceptance/shareholding.

Effective AI adoption requires stakeholder involvement, infrastructural and technological investment, skills development as well as harmonization with Industry 4.0 initiatives and proactive policy support. Comprehensive approaches provide sustainability, efficiency and adherence to environmental and operational best practices.

Recommendations for Further Studies

Future studies should instead develop country-specific case studies to incorporate local environmental, social economic and regulatory settings and should explore the long-term effects of AI in abandoned mining sites to assure its sustainability and efficiency.

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